

Validation Assistant rules EU_PPP
IUCLID 6 version 10 – April 2026

Rule ID	Type	Working context	Target Documents	IUCLID Dataset	Message VA report	IUCLID Release	Status
BR_PPP_001	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Administrative data' is not complete. The 'Endpoint' addressed by the study record must be indicated.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021), 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_002	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Administrative data' is not complete. If you want to submit a data waiving then the rationale for waiving the information requirement must be indicated in the field 'Data waiving' and an appropriate justification must be selected in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. If none of the available justifications in the picklist apply, select 'other:' and provide the justification in the below field. If you wish to provide further information in support of the data waiving, use the field 'Justification for type of information' and/or attach a document under 'Attached justification' heading. A reference to a record with relevant information for the data waiving can be made under 'Cross-reference' heading.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_003	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Administrative data' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the field 'Reliability' must be provided. Note: If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_004	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the 'Reference' entry must be completed. For each reference, the 'Year' or the 'Report date' must always be indicated. In addition, as a minimum, the following must be provided: (Dynamic message is displayed depending on selection in 'Reference type' field) #study report# - If the data is from a study report, the field 'Testing facility' (with the full address of the testing laboratory, including city and country), an entry for Study ID type="notification of Studies (NoS) ID" under 'Other study identifier(s)', either 'Report number' or 'Study number' and 'Title' must be provided. #other company data# - If the data is from a company, either the field 'Report number' or the field 'Study number' must be provided. In addition, information must be given under 'Author', 'Study sponsor' and/or 'Title'. # publication, publication (copyright not owned for reproduction), review article or handbook, secondary source or grey literature# - If the data is from a literature source, the field 'Bibliographic source' must be provided. Sufficient information should be given to be able to identify the literature source. #other: or no selection#	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_005	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', or indicated as a testing proposal, the test guideline (to be) used in the study must be indicated in the 'Guideline' under the 'Test guideline' heading. If you add several entries, then the 'Guideline' must be specified for each of them. If the test guideline applied is not found in the picklist, select 'other:' and provide information on the guideline in the below field. If no test guideline can be specified (e.g. because the study is a non-guideline study, or (Q)SAR was applied), a description of the principles of the test protocol or the method must be provided in the field 'Principles of method if other than guideline'.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_006	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', or indicated as a testing proposal, the test material (to be) used in the study must be identified by linking a test material information (TMI) record in the 'Test material information' entry. The TMI record should contain sufficient information to allow the understanding of the identity of the tested substance. As a minimum, under 'Composition' at least one 'Constituent' must be reported. Each created component must contain at least one of the following identifiers in the designated fields: EC number, CAS number, IUPAC name/ microorganism name. For a read-across target record, the test material information should identify the target substance of the read-across.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_007	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Administrative data' is not complete. This endpoint study record has been indicated with the adequacy 'key study' but the assigned 'Reliability' score indicates that the study is not reliable. A key study is expected to correspond to a robust study summary of sufficient quality and reliability (score 1 or 2) to independently fulfil the information requirements for an endpoint. You are advised to reconsider whether this study is of sufficient quality to be used as key study to fulfil the information requirements for this endpoint.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_008	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Materials and methods' is not complete. In the entry 'Test guideline' the field 'Deviations' has been set to 'yes'. In this case, you are expected to provide a brief explanation summarising the deviations from the guideline in the below 'Remarks' field. More detailed information should be described in the respective fields of the 'Materials and methods' part. Moreover, all possible effects that such a deviation may have on the obtained test results should be analysed and reported in the 'Overall remarks, attachments' part of the endpoint study record.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active

BR_PPP_009	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the entry 'Reference' must be completed. For each reference a version of the full study report must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field in the Literature reference. - If the information is confidential, a sanitised version should be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' and the confidential report should be added under the 'Attached confidential document' field in the Literature reference.	6.4 (April 2020), updated in 6.5 (October 2020), 6.6 (October 2021) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_010	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Data source': is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', report the notification of studies status of the submitted study in the Literature reference entity. If the study has been notified in the Notification of Studies Database then report the number in the 'Other study identifier(s)' - 'Study ID' and indicate Study ID type="notification of Studies (NoS) ID". If the study has not been notified provide a justification in 'Other study identifier(s)' - 'Remarks' field. The 'notification of Studies (NoS) ID' must follow the format: EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNN (where YYYY-year with minimum value set to 2021 and numeric and N-8digit number). A Study ID type of "notification of Studies (NoS) ID" entry must be provided. If the study has been notified in the Notification of Studies Database then the NoS ID must be reported in the 'Study ID' field of the Literature Reference for the study, and indicate select type = 'notification of Studies (NoS) ID' NoS_ID and must follow the format: EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNN (where YYYY-year with minimum value set to 2021 and numeric and N-8digit number). If the study has not been notified, then the 'Remarks' field must be completed providing a justification.	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.6 (April 2022) and in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_011	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_MO_endpoints_all	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one endpoint study record indicated as either a key study, weight of evidence, or data waiving must be provided for this section. Supporting studies should be provided as appropriate, as additional endpoint study records, but they cannot be used to fulfil the information requirement. - To indicate an endpoint study record as a key study or as part of a weight of evidence approach, select 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' in the 'Adequacy of study' picklist and fill in all relevant fields under 'Administrative data', 'Data source', 'Materials and methods', and 'Results and discussion' for this endpoint. Other types of study summaries (e.g. supporting studies) should be filled in as much as possible. - To indicate an endpoint study record as data waiving, make a selection in the field 'Data waiving' and provide a justification in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. #A separate message is displayed for each section.#	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.6 (October 2021), 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_012	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_MO_summaries_all	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one endpoint study summary must be provided for this section.	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.5 (April 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_013	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_Active_Sub_App_endpoints_all	Main Mixture	At least one endpoint study record indicated as either a key study, weight of evidence, or data waiving must be provided for this section. Supporting studies should be provided as appropriate, as additional endpoint study records, but they cannot be used to fulfil the information requirement. - To indicate an endpoint study record as a key study or as part of a weight of evidence approach, select 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' in the 'Adequacy of study' picklist and fill in all relevant fields under 'Administrative data', 'Data source', 'Materials and methods', and 'Results and discussion' for this endpoint. Other types of study summaries (e.g. supporting studies) should be filled in as much as possible. - To indicate an endpoint study record as data waiving, make a selection in the field 'Data waiving' and provide a justification in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. #A separate message is displayed for each section.#	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_014	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_Active_Sub_App_summaries_all	Main Mixture	At least one endpoint study summary must be provided for this section.	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_015	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_MO_endpoints_all	Main Mixture	At least one endpoint study record indicated as either a key study, weight of evidence, or data waiving must be provided for this section. Supporting studies should be provided as appropriate, as additional endpoint study records, but they cannot be used to fulfil the information requirement. - To indicate an endpoint study record as a key study or as part of a weight of evidence approach, select 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' in the 'Adequacy of study' picklist and fill in all relevant fields under 'Administrative data', 'Data source', 'Materials and methods', and 'Results and discussion' for this endpoint. Other types of study summaries (e.g. supporting studies) should be filled in as much as possible. - To indicate an endpoint study record as data waiving, make a selection in the field 'Data waiving' and provide a justification in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. #A separate message is displayed for each section.#	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_016	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_MO_summaries_all	Main Mixture	At least one endpoint study summary must be provided for this section.	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_017	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_Active_Sub_App_endpoints_all	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one endpoint study record indicated as either a key study, weight of evidence, or data waiving must be provided for this section. Supporting studies should be provided as appropriate, as additional endpoint study records, but they cannot be used to fulfil the information requirement. - To indicate an endpoint study record as a key study or as part of a weight of evidence approach, select 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' in the 'Adequacy of study' picklist and fill in all relevant fields under 'Administrative data', 'Data source', 'Materials and methods', and 'Results and discussion' for this endpoint. Other types of study summaries (e.g. supporting studies) should be filled in as much as possible. - To indicate an endpoint study record as data waiving, make a selection in the field 'Data waiving' and	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.5 (April 2021), 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.9 (October 2025)	active

					provide a justification in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. #A separate message is displayed for each section.#		
BR_PPP_018	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	EU_PPP_Active_Sub_App_endpoints_all	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one endpoint study summary must be provided for this section.	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_019	Failure	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_MRL_endpoints_all	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one endpoint study record indicated as either a key study, weight of evidence, or data waiving must be provided for this section. Supporting studies should be provided as appropriate, as additional endpoint study records, but they cannot be used to fulfil the information requirement. - To indicate an endpoint study record as a key study or as part of a weight of evidence approach, select 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' in the 'Adequacy of study' picklist and fill in all relevant fields under 'Administrative data', 'Data source', 'Materials and methods', and 'Results and discussion' for this endpoint. Other types of study summaries (e.g. supporting studies) should be filled in as much as possible. - To indicate an endpoint study record as data waiving, make a selection in the field 'Data waiving' and provide a justification in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. # A separate message is displayed for each section.#	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_020	Failure	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_MRL_summaries_all	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one endpoint study summary must be provided for this section.	6.5 (October 2020), updated in 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_021	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	Mixture composition is incomplete. At least one Mixture composition must be present in the dossier function. This must include a linked substance which has the Function = 'active substance'.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_022	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	For each Active substance composition, at least one constituent must be defined. All constituents must be identified by linking a reference substance. Message (BR_BPR_010 for BPR): Every active substance must be linked to a reference substance.	6.5 (April 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_023	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	At least one document with the type of composition set to 'legal entity composition of the substance' must be provided. Each substance must be identified by at least one specification of purity. Specify the following information: Degree of purity of the active substance Constituents Impurities, if applicable Additives, if applicable Each constituent, impurity and additive must be identified by linking a reference substance, complete with available identifiers and molecular and structural information, and by providing the concentration range. Message (BR_BPR_011 for BPR): Each substance must have at least the specification of purity. Specify the following information:- Degree of purity of the active substance- Constituents- Impurities, if applicable- Additives, if applicableEach constituent, impurity and additive must be identified by linking a reference substance, complete with available identifiers, molecular and structural information, and by providing the concentration range.	6.5 (April 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_024	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, SUBSTANCE	Main Mixture and Active Substance	Each (active) substance must have a reference substance.	6.5 (April 2021), updated in 6.8 (April 2024)	active
BR_PPP_025	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, SUBSTANCE	Main Mixture and Active Substance	Mixture compositions must have the same active substance. Where more than one mixture (product formulation/preparation) is reported, the components with the Function = 'active substance' must be the same. This is confirmed by checking that the substance UUID for each active substance is identical.	6.5 (April 2021), updated in 6.7 (April 2023)	active
BR_PPP_026A	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.GAP	Main Mixture	Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) is incomplete. At least one Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) must be created.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.7 (October 2023) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_026B	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.GAP	Main Mixture	Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) is incomplete.The following fields must be completed: At least one target organism needs to be defined in a GAP. Select the appropriate scientific name from picklist. If the target organism is not listed, select 'other' and text the target organism in the 'other' box. If a scientific name is not relevant or not known, select 'no data'.	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (April 2024) and 6.9 (October 2025)	active

		EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application					
QLT_PPP_027	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Data source' is not complete. The primary literature reference entity must be either a Study report (full) or a Publication or a Publication (copyright not owned for reproduction). Additional literature reference entities with other Reference types can provide supporting information. Note more than one file can be included in a literature reference entity 'Attachments' block if they have the same authors.	6.5 (April 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_028	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition, SUBSTANCE Data selection function: CF_obj_02 See #676220 Instructions for	Main Mixture and Active Substance	Reference substance information is not complete. Each reference substance must contain at least one of the following identifiers in the designated fields: EC number, CAS number, IUPAC name. If you use a reference substance to report (a group of) unknown constituents/impurities, you need to enter in the IUPAC name field: "Unknown constituents/impurities". In addition, you should specify, as far as possible, the number and nature of these unknown constituents/impurities in the 'Remarks' field of the constituent/impurity block.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_029	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition	Main Mixture and Active Substance	Multiple constituents in the active substance composition/purity specification are identified with the same reference substance. Remove the duplicate entries. Message (BR_BPR_013 for BPR): Multiple constituents in the active substance composition/purity specification are identified with the same reference substance. Remove the duplicate entries.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_030	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	The 'Typical concentration' for each Active substance composition constituent should be specified (value and unit). The value should be representative for the substance as manufactured/imported. Active substance composition results shall include quantitative data, in terms of g/kg content, for all components present in quantities of 1 g/kg or more.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_031	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.AnalyticalInformation FLEXIBLE_RECORD.IntermediateEffects FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Manufacturer_EU_PPP	Entire dossier	A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Attached background material' header > 'Attached confidential document' field or 'Overall remarks, attachments' block, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.7 (October 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_032	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.IntermediateEffects FLEXIBLE_RECORD.LiteratureSearch	Entire dossier	Reference' is not complete. For each reference a version of the full study report must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.- If the information is confidential, a sanitised version should be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' and the confidential report should be added under the 'Attached documents' field in the Literature reference	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.10 (April 2026)	active
BR_PPP_033	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. European reference number field must be filled in and the format must be UUID.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
BR_PPP_034	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. European reference number field must be filled in and the format must be UUID.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
BR_PPP_035	Failure	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MAXIMUM_RESIDUE_LEVELS.MRLApplication	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. European reference number field must be filled in and the format must be UUID.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
BR_PPP_036	Failure	EU PPP Basic substance application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. European reference number field must be filled in and the format must be UUID.	6.5 (April 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_037	Warning	Deactivated	DATA_PROTECTION.Confidentiality	Entire dossier	Data protection: If the Confidentiality flag is checked the Justification must be completed.	6.6 (October 2021), deactivated in 6.6 (October 2022)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_037A	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	DATA_PROTECTION.Confidentiality	Entire dossier	'Data protection' is incomplete. If the Confidentiality flag is checked the Justification must be completed. Message (QLT_BPR_009 for BPR): If the Confidentiality flag is set, a Justification must be provided.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_038	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. You have indicated under the 'Joint application' field that the application is a part of a joint submission. In this case you must provide an entry under the 'European joint submission number' field in UUID format.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.7 (April 2023)	active
BR_PPP_039	Failure	Deactivated	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. You have indicated under the 'Joint application' field that the application is a part of a joint submission. Please specify the role in the 'Role in the Joint Submission' field. If the submitter is the lead applicant and the dossier is the main dossier select 'Lead'. If the dossier is submitted by a third party consultant and it is the main dossier select 'Lead'. If the dossier is submitted by a member applicant and is not the main	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (April 2024), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated

					dossier of the joint submission select 'Member applicant'. If the aim of the dossier is to provide supplementary data for the dossier (e.g. by means of a Letter of Access) but the submitter is neither the lead applicant nor a member, select 'Contributor'."		
QLT_PPP_040	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoint_summaries_all	Entire dossier	'Additional information' is incomplete. A public (sanitised) version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the Endpoint study summary document under the 'Attached background material' header > Attached confidential document, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_041	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	Overall remarks, attachments is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the Endpoint study record under the 'Overall remarks, attachments' header > 'Attached (confidential) document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: full study reports and related files should be uploaded in the Literature reference entity of the Data Source.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_042	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP	Entire dossier	'Reports and administrative information' is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Reports and administrative information' header > 'Attached document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_043	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Manufacturer_EU_PPP	Substance	'Additional information' is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Additional information' header > 'Document J' field, but there is no file in the field 'Sanitised Document J'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Sanitised Document J' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Sanitised Document J' field.	6.6 (October 2021)	active
QLT_PPP_044	Warning	Deactivated	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EcotoxRiskAssessmentPesticides	Main Mixture	A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Attached background material' header > 'Attached confidential document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (October 2021), deactivated in 6.6 (April 2022)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_045	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.AquaticToxicityRacReporting FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.DefinitionResidueFate FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EndocrineDisruptingPropertiesAssessmentPest FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcGroundwater FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcOtherRoutes FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcSoil FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcWaterSed FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ExpectedExposure FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Metabolites FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.MRLProposal FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.NonDietaryExpo FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.RelevantMetabolitesGroundWater FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Additional information' header > 'Attached confidential document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_046	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.IntermediateEffects	Substance	A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the 'Attached (confidential) document' field of the Intermediate Effects document (Intermediate effects- mechanistic information) . Upload a sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Full study reports should be included in the literature reference entity.	6.6 (October 2021)	active
BR_PPP_047	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the 'Attachments' block in the Literature Reference entity must be completed. For each 'Attachments' block a version of the attachment must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field, in addition, a selection under the field 'Attachment type' must be filled in. If the information is confidential, the original version should be added under the under the 'Attached confidential document' field in the Literature reference.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_048	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the Reference type specified as study report must have a report provided under the 'Attachments' block and 'Attachment type' must be 'full study report'.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active

BR_PPP_049	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EcotoxRiskAssessmentPesticides	Main Mixture	A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Attached background material' header > 'Attached confidential document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (April 2022), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_050	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FIXED_RECORD.OtherRepresentativeProducts FLEXIBLE_RECORD_MixtureComposition	Entire dossier	Other representative product is incomplete. The Mixture composition must include one linked substance which has the Function = 'active substance'. This substance must be the same in the Main product mixture and in the Other Representative products.	6.6 (October 2021)	active
BR_PPP_051	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. You have indicated under the 'Joint application' field that the application is a part of a joint submission. In this case you must provide an entry under the 'European joint submission number' field in UUID format.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.7 (April 2023)	active
BR_PPP_052	Failure	Deactivated	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete. You have indicated under the 'Joint application' field that the application is a part of a joint submission. Please specify the role in the 'Role in the Joint Submission' field. If the submitter is the lead applicant and the dossier is the main dossier select 'Lead'. If the dossier is submitted by a third party consultant and it is the main dossier select 'Lead'. If the dossier is submitted by a member applicant and is not the main dossier of the joint submission select 'Member applicant'. If the aim of the dossier is to provide supplementary data for the dossier (e.g. by means of a Letter of Access) but the submitter is neither the lead applicant nor a member, select 'Contributor'.	6.6 (October 2021), updated in 6.8 (April 2024), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_053	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ResidueFood	Active Substance	Proposed residue definitions. A Residue definition for enforcement for unprocessed plant/animal products must be provided. Complete a row in the 'Food / feed of plant origin residue definition for monitoring' repeatable block or the 'Food of animal origin residue definition monitoring' repeatable block. The remarks field can be completed if no residue definition is defined.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_054	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ResidueFood	Active Substance	Proposed residue definitions. A Residue definition for risk assessment for unprocessed plant/animal products must be provided. Complete a row in the 'Food / feed of plant origin residue definition risk assessment' repeatable block with Crop Group = primary or 'Food of animal origin residue definition risk assessment'. The remarks field can be completed if no residue definition is defined.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_055	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ResidueFood	Active Substance	Proposed residue definitions. A Residue definition for risk assessment for processed plant/animal products must be provided. Complete a row in the 'Food / feed of plant origin residue definition risk assessment' repeatable block with Crop Group = processed or 'Food of animal origin residue definition risk assessment'. The remarks field can be completed if no residue definition is defined.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_056	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ResidueFood	Active Substance	Proposed residue definitions. A Residue definition for risk assessment for rotational crops must be provided. Complete a row in the 'Food / feed of plant origin residue definition risk assessment' repeatable block with Crop Group = rotational. The remarks field can be completed if no residue definition is defined.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_057	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues	Active Substance	Toxicological reference values have not been provided. Flexible Summary, Toxicological reference values must be completed.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_058	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues	Active Substance	In the Toxicological reference values document the AOEL must be completed unless 'Not allocated' is checked and a justification is provided.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_059	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues	Main Mixture and Active Substance	In the Toxicological reference values document the ADI must be completed. The following fields should be filled in: 'ADI' (range value), 'Study retained', 'Route of original study' and 'Overall uncertainty factor (UF)' unless 'Not allocated' is checked and a justification is provided.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (April and October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_060	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues	Active Substance	In the Toxicological reference values document the ARfD must be completed. The following fields should be filled in 'ARfD' (range value), 'Study retained', 'Route of original study' and 'Overall uncertainty factor (UF)' unless 'Not allocated' is checked and a justification is provided.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (April 2024)	active
BR_PPP_061	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues	Active Substance	In the Toxicological reference values document the AAOEL must be completed unless 'Not allocated' is checked and a justification is provided.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_062	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	Components of the mixture composition. Reference substance information is not complete. The reference substance must contain at least one of the following identifiers in the designated fields: EC number, CAS number, IUPAC name/ microorganism name. In the case of extracts or other cases where an IUPAC name cannot be defined this field should be completed e.g. 'Extract of ginger' or 'Unknown mixture'.	6.5 (April 2021), updated in 6.10 (April 2026)	active

BR_PPP_063	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Administrative data' is not complete. The 'Endpoint' addressed by the study record must be indicated.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_064	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Administrative data' is not complete. If you want to submit a data waiving then the rationale for waiving the information requirement must be indicated in the field 'Data waiving' and an appropriate justification must be selected in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. If none of the available justifications in the picklist apply, select 'other:' and provide the justification in the below field. If you wish to provide further information in support of the data waiving, use the field 'Justification for type of information' and/or attach a document under 'Attached justification' heading. A reference to a record with relevant information for the data waiving can be made under 'Cross-reference' heading.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_065	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Administrative data' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the field 'Reliability' must be provided. Note: If you select 'other:' then the below field must be filled in.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_066	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ResiduesInLivestock	Substance	In the Residues in Livestock document the Dietary burden table must be completed unless 'Remarks' is completed with a justification for not completing the table	6.7 (October 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_067	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', or indicated as a testing proposal, the test guideline (to be) used in the study must be indicated in the 'Guideline' under the 'Test guideline' heading. If you add several entries, then the 'Guideline' must be specified for each of them. If the test guideline applied is not found in the picklist, select 'other:' and provide information on the guideline in the below field. If no test guideline can be specified (e.g. because the study is a non-guideline study, or (Q)SAR was applied), a description of the principles of the test protocol or the method must be provided in the field 'Principles of method if other than guideline'.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_068	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', or indicated as a testing proposal, the test material (to be) used in the study must be identified by linking a test material information (TMI) record in the 'Test material information' entry. The TMI record should contain sufficient information to allow the understanding of the identity of the tested substance. As a minimum, under 'Composition' at least one 'Constituent' must be reported. Each created component must contain at least one of the following identifiers in the designated fields: EC number, CAS number, IUPAC name. For a read-across target record, the test material information should identify the target substance of the read-across.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_069	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Administrative data' is not complete. This endpoint study record has been indicated with the adequacy 'key study' but the assigned 'Reliability' score indicates that the study is not reliable. A key study is expected to correspond to a robust study summary of sufficient quality and reliability (score 1 or 2) to independently fulfil the information requirements for an endpoint. You are advised to reconsider whether this study is of sufficient quality to be used as key study to fulfil the information requirements for this endpoint.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_070	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Materials and methods' is not complete. In the entry 'Test guideline' the field 'Deviations' has been set to 'yes'. In this case, you are expected to provide a brief explanation summarising the deviations from the guideline in the below 'Remarks' field. More detailed information should be described in the respective fields of the 'Materials and methods' part. Moreover, all possible effects that such a deviation may have on the obtained test results should be analysed and reported in the 'Overall remarks, attachments' part of the endpoint study record.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_071	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the entry 'Reference' must be completed. For each reference a version of the full study report must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field in the Literature reference. - If the information is confidential, a sanitised version should be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' and the confidential report should be added under the 'Attached confidential document' field in the Literature reference.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_072	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	Data source: is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', report the notification of studies status of the submitted study in the Literature reference entity. If the study has been notified in the Notification of Studies Database then report the number in the 'Other study identifier(s)' - 'Study ID' and indicate Study ID type="notification of Studies (NoS) ID". If the study has not been notified provide a justification in 'Other study identifier(s)' - 'Remarks' field. The 'notification of Studies (NoS) ID' must follow the format: EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNN (where YYYY-year with minimum value set to 2021 and numeric and N-8digit number). A Study ID type of "notification of Studies (NoS) ID" entry must be provided. If the study has been notified in the Notification of Studies Database then the NoS ID must be reported in the 'Study ID' field of the Literature Reference for the study, and indicate select type = 'notification of Studies (NoS) ID' NoS_ID and must follow the format: EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNN (where YYYY-year with minimum value set to 2021 and numeric and N-8digit number). If the study has not been notified, then the 'Remarks' field must be completed providing a justification.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated

QLT_PPP_073	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	Mixture composition: The composition information for the active substance, safener, synergist or active substance (other not to be assessed) cannot be claimed confidential. Please remove the CBI flag.	6.7 (October 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_074	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoint_summaries_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Additional information' is incomplete. A public (sanitised) version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the Endpoint study summary document under the 'Attached background material' header > Attached confidential document, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_075	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	Overall remarks, attachments is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the Endpoint study record under the 'Overall remarks, attachments' header > 'Attached (confidential) document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: full study reports and related files should be uploaded in the Literature reference entity of the Data Source.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_076	Warning	Deactivated	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Reports and administrative information' is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Reports and administrative information' header > 'Attached document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_077	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.MagnitudeResiduesPlants	Substance	Description of key information is incomplete: At least one item must be created for each 'Summary of key residues data selected from the supervised residue trials'. In addition, for each item created the following fields must be filled in:- 'Study name/type' - 'Relevant gap' - 'Commodity'	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (April 2024)	active
BR_PPP_079	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Mixture (Other representative products)	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the 'Attachments' block in the Literature Reference entity must be completed. For each 'Attachments' block a version of the attachment must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field, in addition, a selection under the field 'Attachment type' must be filled in. If the information is confidential, the original version should be added under the under the 'Attached confidential document' field in the Literature reference.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_080	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition, SUBSTANCE	Main Mixture and Active Substance	Remove CBI flag from the Reference substance linked to the Active Substance.	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_085	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	Section 1: Identity of the plant protection product. A mixture composition document must be completed. Provide details on the formulation.	6.6 (April 2022)	active
BR_PPP_086	Failure	EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	Section 2: Preparation of the substance for use. A mixture composition document must be completed. Provide details on the preparation.	6.6 (April 2022)	active
BR_PPP_087	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	A mixture composition document must be completed. The components of the mixture, preparation or formulation must be listed and associated with a reference substance entity, substance dataset or mixture dataset. For each component the 'Name' field must be completed. Message (BR_BPR_014 for BPR): A mixture composition document must be completed. The components of the mixture, preparation or formulation must be listed and associated with a reference substance entity, substance dataset or mixture dataset. For each component the 'Name' field must be completed.	6.6 (April 2022)	active

BR_PPP_088	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	Mixture composition is incomplete. The component with the Function = 'active substance' must be linked in the 'Name' field to a reference substance or substance dataset.	6.6 (April 2022)	active
BR_PPP_089	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	Mixture composition is incomplete. There must be one component with the Function = 'active substance'. The function 'active substance (other, not to be assessed)' can be used for active substances which are included in the application but not for approval.	6.6 (April 2022)	active
BR_PPP_090	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Basic substance application	Main Mixture FIXED_RECORD.OtherRepresentativeProducts FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Entire dossier	Other representative products/Mixture Composition is not compatible. You have included the Main Mixture as a component of the Other Representative product Mixture and/or Mixture Composition > Components. Note that the Main and Other Representative product Mixture and/or Mixture Composition > Components entities cannot be identical. Remove any duplicate datasets from the Other Representative Product and/or from Mixture Composition > components section.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.7 (April and October 2023)	active
BR_PPP_091	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Administrative data' is not complete. The 'Endpoint' addressed by the study record must be indicated.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_092	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Administrative data' is not complete. If you want to submit a data waiving then the rationale for waiving the information requirement must be indicated in the field 'Data waiving' and an appropriate justification must be selected in the field 'Justification for data waiving'. If none of the available justifications in the picklist apply, select 'other:' and provide the justification in the below field. If you wish to provide further information in support of the data waiving, use the field 'Justification for type of information' and/or attach a document under 'Attached justification' heading. A reference to a record with relevant information for the data waiving can be made under 'Cross-reference' heading.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_093	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Administrative data' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the field 'Reliability' must be provided. Note: If you select 'other:' then the below field must be filled in.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_094	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.BioPropertiesMicro	Active Substance	The Biological Properties of the microorganism summary document must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.8 (April 2024), update in 6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_095	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', or indicated as a testing proposal, the test guideline (to be) used in the study must be indicated in the 'Guideline' under the 'Test guideline' heading. If you add several entries, then the 'Guideline' must be specified for each of them. If the test guideline applied is not found in the picklist, select 'other:' and provide information on the guideline in the below field. If no test guideline can be specified (e.g. because the study is a non-guideline study, or (Q)SAR was applied), a description of the principles of the test protocol or the method must be provided in the field 'Principles of method if other than guideline'.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_096	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', or indicated as a testing proposal, the test material (to be) used in the study must be identified by linking a test material information (TMI) record in the 'Test material information' entry. The TMI record should contain sufficient information to allow the understanding of the identity of the tested substance. As a minimum, under 'Composition' at least one 'Constituent' must be reported. Each created component must contain at least one of the following identifiers in the designated fields: EC number, CAS number, IUPAC name. For a read-across target record, the test material information should identify the target substance of the read-across.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_097	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Administrative data' is not complete. This endpoint study record has been indicated with the adequacy 'key study' but the assigned 'Reliability' score indicates that the study is not reliable. A key study is expected to correspond to a robust study summary of sufficient quality and reliability (score 1 or 2) to independently fulfil the information requirements for an endpoint. You are advised to reconsider whether this study is of sufficient quality to be used as key study to fulfil the information requirements for this endpoint.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_098	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Materials and methods' is not complete. In the entry 'Test guideline' the field 'Deviations' has been set to 'yes'. In this case, you are expected to provide a brief explanation summarising the deviations from the guideline in the below 'Remarks' field. More detailed information should be described in the respective fields of the 'Materials and methods' part. Moreover, all possible effects that such a deviation may have on the obtained test results	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated

					should be analysed and reported in the 'Overall remarks, attachments' part of the endpoint study record.		
BR_PPP_099	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the entry 'Reference' must be completed. For each reference a version of the full study report must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field in the Literature reference. - If the information is confidential, a sanitised version should be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' and the confidential report should be added under the 'Attached confidential document' field in the Literature reference.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_100	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', report the notification of studies status of the submitted study in the Literature reference entity. If the study has been notified in the Notification of Studies Database then report the number in the 'Other study identifier(s)' - 'Study ID' and indicate 'Study ID type="notification of Studies (NoS) ID"'. If the study has not been notified provide a justification in 'Other study identifier(s)' - 'Remarks' field. The 'notification of Studies (NoS) ID' must follow the format: EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNN (where YYYY-year with minimum value set to 2021 and numeric and N-8digit number). A Study ID type of "notification of Studies (NoS) ID" entry must be provided. If the study has been notified in the Notification of Studies Database then the NoS ID must be reported in the 'Study ID' field of the Literature Reference for the study, and indicate select type = 'notification of Studies (NoS) ID' NoS_ID and must follow the format: EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNN (where YYYY-year with minimum value set to 2021 and numeric and N-8digit number). If the study has not been notified, then the 'Remarks' field must be completed providing a justification.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_102	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoint_summaries_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Additional information' is incomplete. A public (sanitised) version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the Endpoint study summary document under the 'Attached background material' header > Attached confidential document, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_103	Warning	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	Overall remarks, attachments is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the Endpoint study record under the 'Overall remarks, attachments' header > 'Attached (confidential) document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: full study reports and related files should be uploaded in the Literature reference entity of the Data Source.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
QLT_PPP_104	Warning	Deactivated	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP	Substance (Metabolites)	'Reports and administrative information' is incomplete. A sanitised version of attachments must be provided. A file has been attached in the document under the 'Reports and administrative information' header > 'Attached document' field, but there is no file in the field 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication'. Upload the sanitised version for publication in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field. Note: if there is no difference between the two files provide a single copy in the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_106	Failure	Deactivated	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Substance (Metabolites)	'Data source' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' the 'Attachments' block in the Literature Reference entity must be completed. For each 'Attachments' block a version of the attachment must be provided under the 'Attached (sanitised) documents for publication' field, in addition, a selection under the field 'Attachment type' must be filled in. If the information is confidential, the original version should be added under the under the 'Attached confidential document' field in the Literature reference.	6.6 (April 2022), deactivated in 6.8 (October 2024)	deactivated
BR_PPP_108	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Pre-application identifier must be entered in this format EFSA-ID-YYYY-NNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_109	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Pre-application identifier must be entered in this format EFSA-ID-YYYY-NNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_110	Failure	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MAXIMUM_RESIDUE_LEVELS	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Pre-application identifier must be entered in this format EFSA-ID-YYYY-NNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_111	Failure	EU PPP Basic substance application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Pre-application identifier must be entered in this format EFSA-ID-YYYY-NNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.10 (April 2026)	active
BR_PPP_112	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Notification of Studies Identifiers must be entered in this format EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_113	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Notification of Studies Identifiers must be entered in this format EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_114	Failure	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MAXIMUM_RESIDUE_LEVELS	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Notification of Studies Identifiers must be entered in this format EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_115	Failure	EU PPP Basic substance application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE	Dossier header	The dossier header is not complete. The Notification of Studies Identifiers must be entered in this format EFSA-YYYY-NNNNNNNNN.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (April 2024) and 6.10 (April 2026)	active

QLT_PPP_116	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ResiduesInLivestock ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ResiduesInLivestock	Active Substance	The flexible summary Residues in Livestock must be provided for this section.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_117	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BiodegradationInSoil ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BiodegradationInWaterAndSedimentSimulationTests ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Hydrolysis	Entire dossier	Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Transformation products'. If 'yes' was selected, the transformation product(s) must be identified under the 'Transformation products' or 'Identity of transformation products' heading by linking the appropriate reference substance(s) in the field 'Identity of compound' or 'Reference Substance' (in ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Hydrolysis).The reference substance can be identified by at least one of the following standard identifiers: EC number, CAS number and/or IUPAC name. If not available, a spectrum must be attached in the table 'Attachments', under 'Overall remarks, attachments' heading. Message FOR QLT_BPR_047: Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Transformation products'. If 'yes' was selected, the transformation product(s) must be identified under the 'Transformation products' or 'Identity of transformation products' heading by linking the appropriate reference substance(s) in the field 'Identity of compound' or 'Reference Substance' (in ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Hydrolysis).The reference substance can be identified by at least one of the following standard identifiers: EC number, CAS number and/or IUPAC name. If not available, a spectrum must be attached in the table 'Attachments', under 'Overall remarks, attachments' heading.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_118	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BiodegradationInSoil	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', at least one of the tables '% Degradation' or 'Disappearance time (DT) of parent compound' must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. - Under the '% Degradation' heading, the fields 'Sampling time', '% Degr.' and 'Parameter' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. - Under the 'Disappearance time (DT) of parent compound' heading, the fields 'Parameter', 'Value' and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_067: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', at least one of the tables '% Degradation' or 'Disappearance time (DT) of parent compound' must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. - Under the '% Degradation' heading, the fields 'Sampling time', '% Degr.' and 'Parameter' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. - Under the 'Disappearance time (DT) of parent compound' heading, the fields 'Parameter', 'Value' and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.7 (April 2023) and 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_119	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ShortTermToxicityToFish	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_120	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AcuteToxicityOral	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_121	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.RepeatedDoseToxicityOral	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level' and 'Basis for effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete. Message for QLT_BPR_054: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level' and 'Basis for effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_122	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.RepeatedDoseToxicityOral	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Critical effects observed' under 'Target system / organ toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'System', 'Organ' and 'Treatment related' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete. Message for QLT_BPR_055: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Critical effects observed' under 'Target system / organ toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'System', 'Organ' and 'Treatment related' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete.	6.6 (October 2022)	active

QLT_PPP_123	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.GeneticToxicityVitro	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Test results' heading, the fields 'Species/strain', 'Metabolic activation', 'Genotoxicity' and 'Cytotoxicity/choice of top concentrations' must be provided. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Overall remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field. Message for QLT_BPR_058: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Test results' heading, the fields 'Species/strain', 'Metabolic activation', 'Genotoxicity' and 'Cytotoxicity/choice of top concentrations' must be provided. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_124	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EndocrineDisruptingPropertiesAssessmentPest	Active Substance	The Flexible Summary Endocrine Disrupting Properties Assessment must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
BR_PPP_125	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.MRLProposal	Active Substance	The Flexible Summary MRL Proposal must be provided and only one document can be created in the Active Substance dataset.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.7 (October 2023) and 6.8 (October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_126	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ExpectedExposure	Active Substance	The Flexible Summary Expected Exposure must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (April and October 2024)	active
BR_PPP_127	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.DefinitionResidueFate	Active Substance	The Flexible Summary Residue definition for risk assessment and environmental monitoring must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_128	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.AquaticToxicityRacReporting	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Effects on aquatic organisms must be provided in the main representative product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022), updated in 6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_129	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.RelevantMetabolitesGroundWater	Active Substance	The Flexible Summary Relevance of metabolites in ground water must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_130	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ResidueFood	Active Substance	The Endpoint Summary Proposed residue definitions must be provided and only one document can be created in the Active Substance dataset.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_131	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EcotoxRiskAssessmentPesticides	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Ecotoxicology Risk Assessment must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_132	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.NonDietaryExpo	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Data on non-dietary exposure must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_133	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Metabolites	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Information on metabolites must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_134	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcSoil	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Estimation of concentrations in soil must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_135	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcGroundwater	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Estimation of concentrations in groundwater must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_136	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcWaterSed	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Estimation of concentrations in surface water and sediment must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.6 (October 2022)	active
QLT_PPP_137	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SkinIrritationCorrosion	Main Mixture and Active Substance	'Results and discussion' is not complete. This endpoint study record has the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' or 'skin corrosion: in vitro / ex vivo' but no result is provided under the 'Results (In vitro)' heading. An endpoint study record marked as 'key study', 'weight of evidence' or 'supporting study' with the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' or 'skin corrosion: in vitro / ex vivo' is expected to have at least one result provided under 'Results (In vitro)' heading. Message for QLT_BPR_063: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. This endpoint study record has the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' or 'skin corrosion: in vitro / ex vivo' but no result is provided under the 'Results (In vitro)' heading. An endpoint study record marked as 'key study', 'weight of evidence' or 'supporting study' with the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' or 'skin corrosion: in vitro / ex vivo' is expected to have at least one result provided under 'Results (In vitro)' heading.	6.7 (October 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_138	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EyelIrritation	Main Mixture and Active Substance	'Results and discussion' is not complete. This endpoint study record has the 'Endpoint' selection 'eye irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' but no result is provided under the 'Results (In vitro / ex vivo / in chemico)' heading. An endpoint study record marked as 'key	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (April 2024)	active

		EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application			study', 'weight of evidence' or 'supporting study' with the 'Endpoint' selection 'eye irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' is expected to have at least one result provided under 'Results (In vitro / ex vivo / in chemico)' heading. Message for QLT_BPR_064: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. This endpoint study record has the 'Endpoint' selection 'eye irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' but no result is provided under the 'Results (In vitro / ex vivo / in chemico)' heading. An endpoint study record marked as 'key study', 'weight of evidence' or 'supporting study' with the 'Endpoint' selection 'eye irritation: in vitro / ex vivo' is expected to have at least one result provided under 'Results (In vitro / ex vivo / in chemico)' heading.		
QLT_PPP_139	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SkinSensitisation	Main Mixture and Substance(s)	'Results and discussion' is not complete. This endpoint study record has the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin sensitisation: in vivo (LLNA)' but no result is provided under the 'Results (in vivo (LLNA))' heading. An endpoint study record marked as 'key study', 'weight of evidence' or 'supporting study' with the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin sensitisation: in vivo (LLNA)' is expected to have at least one result provided under 'Results (in vivo (LLNA))' heading. Message for QLT_BPR_065: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. This endpoint study record has the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin sensitisation: in vivo (LLNA)' but no result is provided under the 'Results (in vivo (LLNA))' heading. An endpoint study record marked as 'key study', 'weight of evidence' or 'supporting study' with the 'Endpoint' selection 'skin sensitisation: in vivo (LLNA)' is expected to have at least one result provided under 'Results (in vivo (LLNA))' heading.	6.7 (October 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_140	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ShortTermToxicityToAqualnv	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If 'other:' was selected in any of the picklists, the below field must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_141	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxicityToAqualnv	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field. Message for QLT_BPR_068: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_142	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToAquaticAlgae	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_143	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToAquaticPlant	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field. Message for QLT_BPR_069: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_144	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToTerrestrialArthropods	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below text field.	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active

QLT_PPP_145	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToTerrestrialPlants	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below text field. Message for QLT_BPR_070: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below text field.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_146	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToBirds	Entire dossier	Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Duration (if not single dose)', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect level' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field. Message for QLT_BPR_071: Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Duration (if not single dose)', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect level' must be filled in, with unit. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_147	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AcuteToxicityInhalation	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_149	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.RepeatedDoseToxicityDermal	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level' and 'Basis for effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete. Message for QLT_BPR_056: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level' and 'Basis for effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete.	6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_150	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.RepeatedDoseToxicityDermal	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Critical effects observed' under 'Target system / organ toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'System', 'Organ' and 'Treatment related' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete. Message for QLT_BPR_057: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Critical effects observed' under 'Target system / organ toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'System', 'Organ' and 'Treatment related' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete.	6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_151	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityReproduction	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', results must be provided for the relevant generations for the selected study design. As a minimum, results for one parental generation (P0, P1) and one offspring generation (F1, F2) must be given. Under the corresponding 'Effect levels' heading, at least the 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level', 'Sex' and 'Basis for effect level', with unit, where applicable, must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field. Message for QLT_BPR_059: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', results must be provided for the relevant generations for the selected study design. As a minimum, results for one parental generation (P0, P1) and one offspring generation (F1, F2) must be given. Under the corresponding 'Effect levels' heading, at least the 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level', 'Sex' and 'Basis for effect level', with unit, where applicable, must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023)	active

QLT_PPP_152	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityReproduction	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Reproductive effects observed' under 'Overall reproductive toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'Treatment related' and 'Relation to other toxic effects' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete. Message for QLT_BPR_060: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Reproductive effects observed' under 'Overall reproductive toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'Treatment related' and 'Relation to other toxic effects' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete.	6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_153	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.DevelopmentalToxicityTeratogenicity	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', results must be provided under the 'Effect levels (maternal animals)' heading and 'Effect levels (fetuses)' heading. In each entry, at least the fields 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level' and 'Basis for effect level' must be provided, with unit where applicable. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field. Message for QLT_BPR_061: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', results must be provided under the 'Effect levels (maternal animals)' heading and 'Effect levels (fetuses)' heading. In each entry, at least the fields 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect level' and 'Basis for effect level' must be provided, with unit where applicable. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_154	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.DevelopmentalToxicityTeratogenicity	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Developmental effects observed' under 'Overall developmental toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'Treatment related' and 'Relation to maternal toxicity' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete. Message for QLT_BPR_062: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', a selection must be made in the field 'Developmental effects observed' under 'Overall developmental toxicity' heading. If 'yes' was selected, then the fields 'Lowest effective dose/conc.', 'Treatment related' and 'Relation to maternal toxicity' must be provided, with unit, where applicable. Each created entry must be complete.	6.7 (April 2023)	active
QLT_PPP_155	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalMethods	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the tables 'Recovery' and 'Repeatability' under the block 'Results using analytical (primary) method' must be complete. The tables must be completed as follows: - 'Recovery', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte, Matrix, Fortification level, Number replicates, Range recovery (%), Mean recovery (%) and RSD (%). - 'Repeatability', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte, Matrix, Number replicates, and RSDr(%). If the endpoint selected is 'methods for relevant impurities and/or metabolites of concern', then also the table 'LOQ/LOD' under the block 'Results using analytical (primary) method' must be complete. The table must be completed as follows: - 'LOQ/LOD', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte and Limit of quantification. If none of the fields can be provided, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks'.	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (April and October 2024), 6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_156	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalMethods	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. You selected 'analytical methods' or 'methods for post-approval control and monitoring purposes' as endpoint. For each of the selected endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the tables 'Recovery' and 'Repeatability' under the block 'Independent laboratory validation (if applicable)' must be complete. The tables must be completed as follows: - 'Recovery', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte, Matrix, Fortification level, Number replicates, Range recovery (%), Mean recovery (%) and RSD (%). - 'Repeatability', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte, Matrix, Number replicates and RSDr (%). If none of the fields can be provided, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks'.	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (April and October 2024), 6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_157	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalMethods	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. You selected one of the following endpoints: - analytical methods - methods for post-approval control and monitoring purposes - methods for relevant impurities and/or metabolites of concern - methods to determine storage stability/shelf life For each of the selected endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the tables 'Recovery' and 'Repeatability' under the block 'Results using confirmatory method (if applicable)' must be complete. The tables must be completed as follows: - 'Recovery', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte, Matrix, Fortification level, Number replicates, Range recovery (%), Mean recovery (%) and RSD (%). - 'Repeatability', for each created entry the following information must be provided: Analyte, Matrix, Number replicates and RSDr (%). If none of the fields can be provided, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks'.	6.7 (October 2023), updated in 6.8 (April and October 2024), 6.9 (October 2025)	active

QLT_PPP_158	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.PathogenicityInfectivityHumans	Active Substance	The Flexible Summary Pathogenicity Infectivity Humans must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
BR_PPP_159	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MAXIMUM_RESIDUE_LEVELS DOSSIER.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE	Dossier header	Dossier header is incomplete: If the submission is an update, the reason for updating must be indicated (Spontaneous update or Official request).- if 'Spontaneous update', a justification under the 'Reason for resubmission' field must be provided; - if 'Official request', the 'Requester' and 'Request Type' must be provided. If in any of the fields none of the available options in the picklist apply, select 'other:' and provide a justification in the field 'other'."	6.7 (April 2023), updated in 6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_160	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.AssessmentOfPotentialToxicity	Main Mixture	The Flexible Summary Assessment of Potential Toxicity must be provided in the Main Product dataset.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_161	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Packaging	Main Mixture	At least one record 'Packaging and compatibility of the preparation with proposed Packaging materials' must be provided in the Product dataset.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_162	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.ProtectionMeasures	Main Mixture and Active Substance	At least one record in 4.1. procedures for cleaning and contaminating of application equipment (Product)/ 1.5.2 recommended methods and precautions concerning handling storage transport or fire (substance) must be provided.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_163	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Ghs	Main Mixture	At least one GHS document must be provided in the Product dataset.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_164	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.LiteratureSearch	Main Mixture and Active Substance	At least one record Literature Data must be provided in both the AS and product datasets.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_165	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Manufacturer_EU_PPP	Main Mixture and Active Substance	At least one Production and quality control record must be provided in the Active Substance dataset.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_166	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.GAP	Main Mixture	Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) is incomplete. Both fields 'Concentration of the target a.s. in dilution' and 'Water amount per treatment / spray volume' must be reported if a dilution was applied.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_167	Warning	EU PPP Basic substance application	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP	Main Mixture	In the 'complementary information' field select the type of bibliography or support documentation provided. If 'other' is selected, the 'remarks' field must be completed.	6.8 (October 2024), updated in 6.9 (October 2025)	active
BR_PPP_168	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MAXIMUM_RESIDUE_LEVELS DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES DOSSIER.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE	Dossier header	The dossier header is incomplete: the dossier name must be provided in the field 'Dossier name (given by user)'	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_169	Warning	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MAXIMUM_RESIDUE_LEVELS	Dossier header	The dossier header is incomplete: The 'Additional information on data requirements' field must always be populated in the MRL dossier header to clarify the rationale for choosing the old or new data requirements.	6.8 (April 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_170	Warning	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition	Main Mixture	Mixture composition is incomplete. The composition unit of the active substance must be expressed in: - CFU/g - CFU/kg - CFU/mL - ITU/mg - ITU/ml - IU/mg - OB/mL - OB/L - OB/g - OB/kg - Cells/mL - Cells/L - Spores/g - Spores/mL.	6.8 (April 2024), update in 6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_171	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	EU_PPP_endpoints_all	Entire dossier	'Materials and methods' is not complete. the test material (to be) used in the study should contain sufficient information to allow the understanding of the identity of the tested substance. Under 'Composition' each created component must contain the concentration and at least one 'Constituent' must be reported.	6.8 (October 2024), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_172	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	MIXTURE.OwnerLegalEntity SUBSTANCE.OwnerLegalEntity	Main Mixture and Active Substance	If the legal entity owner of the mixture composition is the same as the legal entity owner of the active substance, no CBI can be requested. Please remove the CBI flag from the mixture legal entity owner in the product dataset.	6.8 (October 2024)	active
QLT_PPP_173	Warning	Deactivated	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Impurities FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition	Main Mixture and Active Substance	The Reference substance associated to any impurities of type='relevant' in the Impurities section should correspond to the Reference substance marked as 'This impurity is considered relevant for the classification and labelling of the substance' in the Specification of purity of the active substance in g/kg. section of the active substance dataset.	6.8 (October 2024), deactivated in 6.9 (May 2025)	deactivated

QLT_PPP_174	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Melting	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Melting / freezing point' heading at least one of the fields 'Melting / freezing pt.', 'Decomp. temp.' or 'Subl. temp' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_043: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Melting / freezing point' heading at least one of the fields 'Melting / freezing pt.', 'Decomp. temp.' or 'Subl. temp' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.8 (October 2024), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_175	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BoilingPoint	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Boiling point' heading, the fields 'Boiling. pt.' and 'Atm. press.', or the fields 'Decomposition' and 'Decomp. temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_044: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Boiling point' heading, the fields 'Boiling. pt.' and 'Atm. press.', or the fields 'Decomposition' and 'Decomp. temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.8 (October 2024), updated in 6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_176	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BoilingPoint ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.FlashPoint ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Melting ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Partition ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SurfaceTension ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Vapour ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.WaterSolubility	Entire dossier	'Materials and methods' is not complete. For each endpoint study record in this section marked as 'key study' the 'Type of method' must be provided. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. #A separate message is displayed for each section, and each failing record.#	6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_177	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	4.6_Vapour_pressure, ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Vapour	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Vapour pressure' heading, the fields 'Vapour pressure' and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. In addition, the vapour pressure at 20 °C or 25 °C shall be reported. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_045: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Vapour pressure' heading, the fields 'Vapour pressure' and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. In addition, the vapour pressure at 20 °C or 25 °C shall be reported. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_178	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.GeneralInformation	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the field 'Physical state at 20°C and 1013 hPa' must be filled in. In addition, the field 'Form' should be filled in if relevant.	6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_179	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Partition	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Partition coefficient' heading, the fields 'Type', 'Partition coefficient', 'Temp.' and 'pH' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_046: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Partition coefficient' heading, the fields 'Type', 'Partition coefficient', 'Temp.' and 'pH' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_180	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	4.21_Dissociation_constant ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.DissociationConstant	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the field 'Dissociating properties' must be filled in. If the value 'yes' is selected in the picklist, then at least one entry must be created under the 'Dissociation constant' heading with the fields 'pKa' and 'Temp.' provided with unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined for the dissociation constant despite indicating that the substance has dissociating properties, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_066: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', the field 'Dissociating properties' must be filled in. If the value 'yes' is selected in the picklist, then at least one entry must be created under the 'Dissociation constant' heading with the fields 'pKa' and 'Temp.' provided with unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined for the dissociation constant despite indicating that the substance has	6.9 (May 2025)	active

					dissociating properties, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.		
QLT_PPP_181	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EffectivenessAgainstTargetOrganisms	Entire dossier	'General Information' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effects in harmful organisms' heading, the fields - function addressed - product type - Field of use envisaged / User - effect on target organisms must be filled in. If '(Possible) Occurrence of resistance' is not available, provide a justification. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_182	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SolubilityOrganic	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Solubility in organic solvents / fat solubility' heading, the fields 'Medium', 'Solubility', and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. In addition, if the solubility is less than than 250 g/L, also the solubility at 20 °C or 25 °C shall be reported. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If 'other:' was selected in any of the picklists, the below field 'other' must be filled in. Message for QLT_BPR_072: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Solubility in organic solvents / fat solubility' heading, the fields 'Medium', 'Solubility', and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. In addition, if the solubility is less than than 250 g/L, also the solubility at 20 °C or 25 °C shall be reported. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If 'other:' was selected in any of the picklists, the below field 'other' must be filled in.	6.9 (May 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_183	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AcuteToxicityDermal	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect levels' heading, the fields 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect level' must be provided, with unit. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_184	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BiodegradationInWaterScreeningTests	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the '% Degradation' heading, the fields 'Parameter', 'Value' and 'Sampling time' must be filled in with unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_073: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the '% Degradation' heading, the fields 'Parameter', 'Value' and 'Sampling time' must be filled in with unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_185	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToMicroorganisms	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in, with unit. If 'other:' was selected in any of the picklists, the below field must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_186	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToSoilMacroorganismsExceptArthropods	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in, with unit. If 'other:' was selected in any of the picklists, the below field must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_187	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToSoilMicroorganisms	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each endpoint study record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in, with unit. If 'other:' was selected in any of the picklists, the below field must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If none of the available picklist values apply, select 'other:' and provide the reason for not determining a quantitative result in the below text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_188	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SurfaceTension	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Surface tension' heading, the fields 'Surface tension', 'Temp.' and 'Conc.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active

QLT_PPP_189	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.WaterSolubility	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', one of the following tables must be filled in - Water solubility - Solubility of metal ions in aqueous media Under the 'Water solubility' heading the fields 'Water solubility', 'Temp.' and 'pH' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. Under the 'Solubility of metal ions in aqueous media' heading, the fields 'Type of test', 'Mean dissolved conc.' and 'Element analysed' must be filled in, with unit. If 'other:' was selected under 'Type of test', must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result' of the appropriate table. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_190	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AutoFlammability	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', one of the following tables must be filled in: - Auto-ignition temperature (liquids / gases) - Relative self-ignition temperature (solids) Under the 'Auto-ignition temperature (liquids/gases)' heading, the fields 'Auto-ignition temperature' and 'Atm. press.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. Under the 'Relative self-ignition temperature (solids)' heading, the field 'Relative self-ignition temperature' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_191	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AdsorptionDesorption	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', at least one of the tables 'Adsorption coefficient' or 'Partition coefficients' must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. Under the 'Adsorption coefficient' heading, the fields 'Type' and 'Value' must be filled in. If either 'Kd' or 'log Kd' were selected under 'Type', then the field '% Org. carbon' must also be filled in. -Under the 'Partition coefficients' heading, the fields 'Type' and 'Value' must be filled in. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field. Message for QLT_BPR_074: 'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', at least one of the tables 'Adsorption coefficient' or 'Partition coefficients' must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. Under the 'Adsorption coefficient' heading, the fields 'Type' and 'Value' must be filled in. If either 'Kd' or 'log Kd' were selected under 'Type', then the field '% Org. carbon' must also be filled in. -Under the 'Partition coefficients' heading, the fields 'Type' and 'Value' must be filled in. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_192	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BiodegradationinWaterAndSedimentSimulationTests	Substance	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', at least one of the tables '% Degradation' or 'Disappearance time (DT) of parent compound' must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. - Under the '% Degradation' heading, the fields 'Sampling time', '% Degr.' and 'Parameter' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. - Under the 'Disappearance time (DT) of parent compound' heading, the fields 'Compartment', 'Parameter', 'Value' and 'Temp.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_193	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.DissociationConstant ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.WaterSolubility	Active Substance	'Results and discussion' is not complete. The pKa value of the active substance in the dissociation in water document is 2 < pKa < 12. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Water solubility' heading, there should be at least one row where the pH value is: - pH = 4 or pH = 5 - pH = 9 or pH = 10 If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_194	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.RepeatedDoseToxicity ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.RepeatedDoseToxicityOral	Active Substance	'Key value for assessment' is not complete. At least one document summarizing the endpoint 'short-term repeated dose toxicity: oral' has to be created. For each of the created summaries, the following fields must be completed: - Under the header 'Key value for assessment', the field 'endpoint conclusion – systemic effects, oral route' must be filled in. - Under the 'Oral route' heading, the fields 'dose descriptor', 'effect level', and 'experimental exposure time per week' must be filled in with unit when such field is available.	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_196	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	FLEXIBLE_RECORD.ProtectionMeasures	Entire dossier	'Possibility of destruction or decontamination following release in or on the following' is not complete. For each document created, the following fields must be completed: - water, including drinking water - soil	6.9 (October 2025)	active
QLT_PPP_197	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.FlashPoint	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Flash point' heading, the fields 'Flash point' and 'Atm. press.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_198	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms -	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Explosiveness	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Results of test series for explosives' heading, the fields 'Test series', 'Method', 'Parameter', 'Value' and 'Result' must be filled in. Each created entry must be	6.10 (April 2026)	active

		active substance application (product)			complete. If a quantitative result was not determined for the 'Value' and 'Result' fields, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.		
QLT_PPP_199	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.OxidisingProperties	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Test results (Oxidising gases)' heading, the fields 'Parameter' and 'Result' must be filled in. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined for the 'Result' field, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_200	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.OxidisingProperties	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Test result (Oxidising liquids)' heading, the fields 'Sample tested', 'Parameter' and 'Result' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined for the 'Sample tested' and 'Result' fields, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_201	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.OxidisingProperties	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Test result (Oxidising solids)' heading, the fields 'Sample tested', 'Parameter' and 'Result' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined for the 'Sample tested' and 'Result' fields, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_202	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxToFish	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor' and 'Effect conc.' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_203	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BioaccumulationAquaticSediment	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Bioaccumulation factor' heading, the fields 'Type' and 'Value' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_204	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SedimentToxicity	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_205	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToSoilArthropods	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active
QLT_PPP_206	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToBees	Entire dossier	'Results and discussion' is not complete. For each record marked as 'key study' or 'weight of evidence', under the 'Effect concentrations' heading, the fields 'Duration', 'Dose descriptor', 'Effect conc.' and 'Basis for effect' must be filled in with the unit where such a field is available. Each created entry must be complete. If a quantitative result was not determined, an explanation must be provided in the field 'Remarks on result'. If you select 'other:' from any of the picklists, you must specify it in the corresponding free text field.	6.10 (April 2026)	active

Submission portal

Rule ID	Type	Working context	Target - (Checked field reference)	Message	IUCLID Release
BR900	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	Dossier UUID	Same dossier should not be submitted twice (compares dossier UUID's)	Submission portal
BR903	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product)	Legal entity	Legal entity in 'EU PPP Active substance application (product)': Submitting Legal entity in Portal must be same as Legal entity owner in IUCLID (compares legal entity UUID's)	Submission portal
BR904	Failure	EU PPP Basic substance application	Legal entity	Legal entity in 'EU PPP Basic substance application': Submitting Legal entity in Portal must be same as Legal entity owner in IUCLID (compares legal entity UUID's)	Submission portal
BR905	Failure	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	Legal entity	Legal entity in 'EU PPP Microorganisms – active substance application (product)': Submitting Legal entity in Portal must be same as Legal entity owner in IUCLID (compares legal entity UUID's)	Submission portal
BR906	Failure	EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application	Legal entity	Legal entity in 'EU PPP MRL application': Submitting Legal entity in Portal must be same as Legal entity owner in IUCLID (compares legal entity UUID's)	Submission portal
BR907	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	EuropeanReferenceNumber	Indicated 'European reference number' should not be associated with different substances in ECHA Submission Portal. (compares EC number/CAS number/IUPAC names of 'Substance' and 'Reference substance' datasets that are marked to be 'Active substances')	Submission portal
BR908	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	EuropeanReferenceNumber	Indicated 'European reference number' should not be associated with other legal entities in ECHA Submission Portal. (compares legal entity UUID's)	Submission portal
BR909	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance	EuropeanReferenceNumber	Indicated 'European reference number' should not be associated with other PPP dossier types in ECHA Submission Portal	Submission portal

		application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application			
BR910	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic substance application	Storage	Dossier could not be imported in EFSA Agency IUCLID (When a PPP dossier passes IUCLID VA and Submission Portal rules but doesn't get stored in EFSA Agency IUCLID then a relevant BR is logged on the validation report of the dossier's submission)	Submission portal
BR911	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EuropeanReferenceNumber	When submitting an update for a successful notification, the same 'European reference number' must be used to ensure that dossiers are correctly linked. There is already a successful notification for the same dossier type, purpose of the application, confirmatory information status, legal entity, and active substance. Therefore, it appears that this notification should have used the same 'European reference number' [dynamic content: ERN number of the first successful submission related to the under-examination ERN]	Submission portal
BR912	Failure	EU PPP Safeners and synergists application	Legal entityY	The submitting legal entity in the Portal must be the same as the legal entity indicated in the dossier in section '1.1 Identity of the plant protection product, trade name or proposed trade name, and applicant' in field 'Legal entity owner' as duty holder.	Submission portal
BR913	Failure	EU PPP Safeners and synergists application	EuropeanReferenceNumber	The 'European reference number' you provided is already associated with another safener/synergist substance(s) in an EFSA Application submitted in the ECHA Submission Portal. If you need to correct the substance identifiers (EC number, CAS number, or IUPAC name), please contact EFSA for further instructions on how to proceed.	Submission portal
BR914	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EuropeanReferenceNumber	Indicated 'European reference number' should not be associated with different 'Purpose of the application' status in ECHA Submission Portal	Submission portal
BR915	Failure	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	EuropeanReferenceNumber	Indicated 'European reference number' should not be associated with different 'Confirmatory information' checkbox status in ECHA Submission Portal	Submission portal
QLT732	Warning	EU PPP Active substance application (product) EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) EU PPP Maximum residue levels (MRL) application EU PPP Basic	Storage	The maximum number (500) of IUCLID Validation Assistant rules that can be reported for the submitted dossier has been exceeded	Submission portal

		substance application			
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